

**PEDRI GOOD PRACTICE STANDARDS WORKSHOP
2024**

Executive summary

Two workshops involving the public, and involvement and engagement professionals were organised to get feedback on the seven PEDRI Good Practice Standards. The table provides a summary of the discussion:

Standard	Key points
Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Clear and simple language; avoid jargon. -Address practical challenges in engaging diverse groups.
Data Literacy and Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Clarify terms like "data literacy"; avoid vague terms. -Two-way training for both researchers and the public. - Use visual scales, trained facilitators, and adaptable materials.
Effective Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Simplify language; avoid divisive terms. - Focus on understanding data, building trust, and addressing digital exclusion. - Ensure communication is timely and co-produced.
Proactive Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Remove acronyms; use clear and consistent terms. - Build transparency through trust using community ambassadors and campaigns. - Address complexities of transparency in data research.
Mutual Benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Clearly communicate benefits of public involvement. - Ensure fairness of opportunity; use diverse strategies based on feedback. -Incentivise engagement; use impact assessments.
Meaningful Engagement and Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Remove acronyms; clarify terms like "meaningful". - Ongoing evaluation to define meaningful involvement. - Empower participants; tailor involvement throughout the research process.
Create a Culture of PIE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Simplify language; clarify terms like "culture" and "value". - Address private sector and commercial interests realistically. - Involve senior leaders; ensure patient outcomes are central. - Develop measures to embed public engagement and acknowledge contributors.

Introduction:

Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative (PEDRI) is a sector-wide partnership that brings together organisations working with data and statistics to generate insights that can inform policy and practice. The initiative aims to foster collaboration to advance good public involvement and engagement (PIE) practices within data research, to bring the views of the public to policymakers and data holders in a meaningful way.

This report summarises feedback from two workshops held to consider the Good Practice Standards. These standards have been developed with stakeholders, PIE professionals, academics, public members, representatives from the voluntary community and social enterprise (VCSE) sector, and the NHS Transformation Directorate. The first workshop was organised for members of the public, and the second workshop was for PIE professionals. Both these workshops were held online on Zoom and were facilitated by PEDRI's external consultants, Stand.

The word-cloud below provides an overview of the discussions of the two workshops.

Themes

At the conclusion of the two workshops, feedback from the two sessions were analysed and the following themes were identified:

Language: Is this easy to understand?

This theme focuses on communication, i.e., how the standard is written. When participants spoke on the theme of language, they discussed if the language

1. avoided complex jargon and technical terms
2. was easy to understand and avoided convoluted sentences
3. was consistent in the use of terminology

Practice: Can this be implemented?

This theme focuses on the practical aspects of implementing the standards. When participants spoke about practice, they discussed

1. strategies that work in real-life situations
2. barriers and complexities that need to be addressed for the standards to have real world impact

Framework: Is this conceptually sound?

This theme focuses on the structural and conceptual elements of how the standard is framed. When participants spoke about framework, they discussed

1. identification of missing categories
2. need to redefine or rethink categories and concepts in the standard

Standard 1: Equity, diversity, and inclusion

“Effective PIE requires equity of representation of different members of the public, irrespective of their background, experiences, and identities. Inclusivity requires actively seeking out diverse voices and proactively adapting engagement and involvement approaches to make them accessible. PIE should broaden the public audience to new communities and those less familiar with the topic”

Acronyms and jargon:

The public group stressed the importance of clear and simple language, and often remarked that the standard was “wordy”.

“It makes more sense to say “we are all part of diverse communities” instead of complex terms like “equity of representation”. Graduate-level language puts people off, especially those that need to be part of the conversation but don’t have a university education”

Non-English speakers:

Both groups were concerned with how the standard with its complex language would be translated for non-English speakers.

Equality vs Equity:

Both groups said the standards needed to be clear when using technical terms and balance the need for detailed information whilst maintaining clarity and simplicity for the public.

“Will everyone have the same understanding of “equity” and how it differs from “equality”? Standards sound quite technical - the spirit of their intention needs to be easy to grasp and unambiguous”

Representation:

The professional group said the use of ‘representation’ in the standard needed to be more thought through. Representation often entails one person speaking for an entire community. This can be problematic since not everyone shares the same views. They also felt that representativeness should be tailored to meet the needs of the project and not be a tick-box exercise.

“It’s not practical to include representation from every part of society so decisions about who to include should be project specific – looking at what you need to know and thinking about who could best help with this.”

Diversity:

The professional group suggested integrating the nine-protected characteristics into the standards to avoid tokenism and to include EDI.

Implementing the standard:

Whilst the public group spoke about their apprehensions in implementing the standard, the professional group discussed ways this standard could be implemented in practice.

“...very difficult to involve certain groups of people, like young people, people in full-time employment, people of certain communities”

“Should take a variety of approaches – need to think more creatively than the traditional engagement methods. This would enrich the feedback and give us things we might miss out on through tried and tested routes and talking to the same people.”

Suggestions to implement Standard 1 included:

- removing language barriers
- collaborating with VCS organisations
- using simple, inclusive language and infographics in communication
- targeted engagement
- being culturally competent while engaging with diverse communities

Standard 2: Data Literacy and Training

“Effective data literacy, training, and supporting members of the public to have the vocabulary, confidence, and understanding.”

Training for the researchers as well as the public:

Public contributors as well as professionals said the standard needed to be revised to suggest two-way training, instead of training only for the public. In its current form, the standard focuses on the gaps in the public’s skills in engaging with data research, but does not acknowledge researchers limited skills in engaging with the public, and therefore seems undemocratic.

“It’s not just training, supporting members of the public. I wonder how many researchers would need assistance to be able to explain their research in terms of appropriate data, literacy, and training on what people need to know in order to participate in their project”

Clear and easy to understand:

Both the groups thought the standard could be revised further so it is easy to understand.

“Effective data literacy-what does that actually mean?”

They suggested

- explaining what data literacy is
- not using terms like confidence, or understanding in the standard since it raises questions about context, i.e. confidence to do what?

Implementing the standard:

Suggestions to implement Standard 2 included:

- creating a visual scale to represent complexity of data literacy requirements
- ensuring training materials are easy for everyone to understand
- using trained facilitators
- creating information kiosks in hospitals, GP surgeries and other public places
- creating warm, inviting spaces where the public feel comfortable, for example, offering light refreshments and using local or community venues.
- producing training materials that are easily adaptable for different audiences and needs

Standard 3: Effective Communication

“Effective two-way communication and dialogue supports meaningful data research. Enabling all parties to understand one another, and meaningfully contribute to discussions.”

Clear and easy to understand:

Both the groups said the language used in the standard could be simpler and should avoid reinforcing a divide between the research community and the public. Instead, it should emphasise the benefits of inclusive dialogue for everyone involved.

“What is proactively engaging?”

“You just need to say that you will talk to and work with everyone. Waffle makes people think there is a hidden agenda”

“I think the standard is a bit garbled. It says, “dialogue supports meaningful data research”. Well, what do you mean? Do you mean the research is meaningful or the data is meaningful?”

Timely, coproduced communication:

The professional group suggested for communication to be effective it not only needed to be two-way, and proactive, but also co-produced and timely, and therefore these could be integrated into the standard.

Implementing the standard:

Major themes for discussion were around

- understanding what “data” is

- building trust around data
- digital exclusion
- non-text based communication

“...if the people do not understand what the data is all about there's not going to be communication. They need an understanding of what is being asked of them in order for communication to be effective. I think it's more than having an opinion for data research”

“We need to get rid of the stigma attached to the word, data. The word data has achieved misinformation, disinformation, a fear, phobia, a stigma, and a life all of its own”

“We've got to recognise that technology is making some groups more isolated...elderly people that haven't got a computer...with rural communities there are impediments to communicating”

Suggestions to implement Standard 3, included:

- inclusive communication practices that took into account needs of non-English speakers, neurodiverse audiences, and people with disabilities.
- targeted engagement to build trust as a first step before attempting to involve communities in data research
- ensuring those who lack digital access are engaged through tailored strategies
- simple and easy-to-understand language

Standard 4: Proactive transparency

“Working openly throughout all PIE activities, to create a comfortable environment for all parties. Project information must be freely accessible for discussions with members of the public.”

Acronyms, clear and consistent language:

Both groups asked for acronyms to be removed and the language to be clear and consistent. They said:

- terms used in the standards like, “openly” and “comfortable” were vague.
- “project information” needs to be replaced since it is inconsistent with the terminology used in previous standards. The standards are not about projects.
- there needs to be clarity about the use of data and information in the standard.

Meaningful rather than proactive transparency:

Both groups spoke about the complexities in making data research transparent since confidentiality is one of the core operational principles of data research. Participants said it would be useful to explore other terms that reflect the realities of data research.

Implementing the standard:

Building transparency through trust was discussed as a major theme in translating the standard in practice.

“Transparency is essential to building trust, so it underpins everything else”

Suggestions to build trust included:

- building a network of trusted community ambassadors
- local and national campaigns to inform the ways in which data from the public is used, including the regulatory differences in the Four Nations.

Standard 5: Mutual benefit

“PIE activities should enable mutual benefit between all those involved. Researchers should gain new insights/ideas to develop more impactful research informed by public views.”

Clarity about how it is beneficial for the public:

Both groups stressed the importance of clearly communicating the benefits of public involvement to encourage participation. In its current form the standard says how the researchers would benefit but not the public.

Fairness of opportunity:

Some participants from the professional group mentioned there needs to be fairness of opportunity so diverse sections of the public benefit from engaging with research, and researchers can be informed by new ideas and perspectives.

“What we need is more diverse perspectives and narratives. This is why I struggle with this particular standard, because they talk the talk, but they don't walk in the way...there's people's faces that have been in other groups, numerous times. In that case, to me, they're not being transparent, open and offering the opportunities widely”

Implementing the standard:

Suggestions to implement standard 5 included:

- incentivising engagement and involvement informed by public needs example, developing skills, financial compensations etc
- exploring diverse strategies based on feedback and impact assessments

Standard 6: Meaningful engagement and involvement

“Meaningful PIE should take place at every stage of research with clear objectives. PIE should be focused with clear tasks, purpose, and impact, while avoiding tokenism.”

Acronyms and clarity in the terms used:

The professional group suggested removing acronyms in the standard and explaining what was implied by “meaningful”

Concepts are contextual:

Both groups spoke about how concepts like “meaningful” and “tokenism” could be contextual and suggested exercising caution whilst using them. They said what is considered meaningful should be flexible and co-created with the public.

“What as a member of the public, I could see as tokenism, a researcher might think is meaningful PPIE, if they're not very experienced or they're trying to cut corners or they don't have enough funding.”

“What is meaningful? It could mean something different to every single person involved. I think it's capturing that. It's about deciding what that looks like with that group of people at the outset”

Implementing the standard:

The professional group spoke at length about challenges in practising meaningful involvement and engagement, and the lack of consensus in what constitutes meaningful involvement and engagement.

“There needs to be a proper meeting of minds by the public involvement community and the researchers, because a lot of researchers still see public involvement and engagement as a chore. It shouldn't be seen as a chore; it should be seen as a partnership. It is a tough nut to crack, but we need to crack it because otherwise, none of this will work”

“One of the great downfalls of medical research is that it sits on the shelf gathering dust. It's not used because it's either superseded or it was a great solution, but patients couldn't get their heads around it and wouldn't engage with it. If you have proper public involvement from the very, very beginning, it should get rid of all that”

“Find out through one-to-one chats what people's skills and interests are. For example, they might like to review documents rather than contribute to meetings. Or they might like to be involved in the project steering group”

Suggestions to implement the standard in practice included:

- ongoing evaluation and feedback to determine what is considered meaningful throughout the research process
- empowering people to get involved beyond basic tasks like reading, reviewing, commenting

- ensuring people gain new skills by being involved in projects
- involving the public at every stage from the initial study
- tailored involvement and engagement

Standard 7: Creating a culture of PIE

“Creating a culture of PIE in an organisation at every level. Organisations should value PIE and embed it in their institution.”

Acronyms and simple language:

The public group suggested removing acronyms and revising the language to make it easier to understand. The public group also said using technical terms like culture and value was vague and unnecessary.

Acknowledging the presence of the private sector and commercial interests:

The professional group said whilst creating a culture of public engagement and involvement across the organisation was important, the reality of commercial interests in data research, especially that of pharmaceutical industry should be taken into account. The group was concerned that pushing for public engagement and involvement in the private sector would have its challenges.

“The standard seems to be directed at the public sector. But there are certain dynamics in the private sector and it would be a hell of a battle to get people to adopt the different standards that are being proposed here. Some of them might be adopted, I think, in a more nuanced fashion, but they need to take account of the realities of the commercial world”

“...there is a very big blur between public and private provision”

Implementing the standard in practice:

Suggestions to implement the standard in practice included:

- participation of senior leaders in public engagement and involvement to give it legitimacy
- keeping patient outcomes and patient benefits at the center of research
- including a budget for public engagement and involvement in every project at the funding stage
- creating concrete measures to record successful embedding of public engagement and involvement in research
- acknowledging public contributors in diverse ways, for example, having them as co-authors, providing opportunities to present at conferences etc.
- creating a feedback mechanism so public contributors are informed about the impact of their involvement

Conclusion: Improving the standards

The workshop underscored the need for a multifaceted approach to public involvement and engagement (PIE) that addresses key issues across the themes of Language, Practice, and Framework. The recommendations provided are designed to enhance the clarity, inclusivity, and effectiveness of the PEDRI Good Practice Standards.

- **Language:** There is a critical need for the standards to be easily understandable, with clear technical terms and consistent terminology throughout. Simplifying language would not only make the PEDRI standards more accessible but also ensure that all stakeholders can fully engage with the process.
- **Framework :** The conceptual framework of a few standards could be redefined to better reflect the realities of public engagement. This includes addressing the intersection of public and commercial interests, acknowledging the training needs of researchers to engage with the public.
- **Practice:** Successful implementation would require measuring impact of engagement and involvement, continuous feedback mechanisms and ensuring that senior management is visibly involved in public engagement efforts. Additionally, PIE practices must be tailored, fair, and inclusive, and recognise the diverse needs and contributions of all participants. This approach would help to build trust and credibility, making public involvement more meaningful and impactful.